

THE EFFECT OF BRAND IMAGE ON CUSTOMER LOYALTY OF MS GLOW

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Abstract:

Nowadays, appearance is the most essential element in society, and people use cosmetics to meet the expectations of modern look. According to reports from the Central Agency on Statistics (CAS) for the first quarter of 2020, the pharmaceutical, chemical, and traditional medicine sectors, including cosmetics, expanded 5.59%. This indicates that the cosmetic business in Indonesia is growing significantly every year. MS Glow is one of the cosmetics companies that is now experiencing significant growth. A skincare and cosmetics product called MS Glow was established in 2013. MS Glow keeps expanding every year. In fact, MS Glow established a beauty clinic in 2017. MS Glow has also won a number of major awards, including the Indonesia Best Brand Award (IBBA) prize in 2020 and the Marketeers OMNI Brands of The Year prize for two consecutive years, in 2020 and 2021. However, a few months ago, MS Glow had some unsettling problems, leading to several customer complaints concerning MS Glow products. A new trend has emerged on TikTok social media, which includes unsatisfactory testimonies from MS Glow customers. In this trend, disappointment is not just experienced by one individual, but it is experienced by many. Consequently, a large number of consumers are less confident in MS Glow's products. The purpose of this study is to examine the impacts of the strength of brand association favorability of brand association, and uniqueness of brand association on MS Glow customer loyalty. This study employs a survey method together with a quantitative approach. The findings of this study reveal that there is an effect between the strength of brand association, favorability of brand association, and uniqueness of brand association on customer loyalty, it can be concluded that brand image has an affect towards MS Glow customer loyalty in general.

Keywords: Brand Image, Customer Loyalty, MS Glow

1. INTRODUCTION

Many changes happened along with the times, including a shift toward a more sophisticated way of living. One of them is appearance, which is what most influences people's lifestyles. In today's world, where the expectations of trendy appearance force individuals to use cosmetics, appearance is currently the most essential factor. According to reports from the Central Agency of Statistics (CAS), the pharmaceutical, chemical, and traditional medicine sectors, which include cosmetics, expanded by 5.59% in the first quarter of 2020.

This indicates that the cosmetic business in Indonesia is growing significantly every year. According to the Association of Indonesian Cosmetics Companies and Associations (Indonesian AICCA), the market for cosmetics in Indonesia is expected to expand by around 7% in 2021. MS Glow is one of the cosmetics companies that is now experiencing significant growth. Established in 2013, MS Glow is a skincare and cosmetics company. Every year, MS Glow expands, and in 2017, the company even managed to develop a beauty clinic. MS Glow has also won a number of major awards, including the Indonesia Best Brand Award (IBBA) in

2020 and the Marketers OMNI Brands of The Year award for two consecutive years, in 2020 and 2021. According to Suara.com, MS Glow got an award from IRM (Indonesian Record Museum) for becoming successful in marketing its products and having the largest network in Indonesia, with 78,147 subscribers. According to statistics from Kompas.co.id, MS Glow is also the top-selling local skincare product in the online marketplace, with sales totaling Rp. 38.5 billion from January 1 to February 18, 2021.

However, at the end of the previous month, MS Glow had unsettling problems, and several MS Glow customers voiced their complaints about the company's products. According to the online news source Jember Network, a new social media trend containing unsatisfactory testimonies from MS Glow customers has arisen on TikTok. In this trend, more than one individual feels the disappointment. Several people share the same sentiment. Consequently, a large number of consumers are less confident in MS Glow's products. Even though there were several negative stories concerning MS Glow goods, strangely, MS Glow sales statistics still showed a very noticeable growth. The author is intrigued to learn more about the effect of brand image towards MS Glow customer loyalty.

The author identifies brand image as the study's independent variable (X), while customer loyalty serves as the study's dependent variable (Y). Additionally, this study is helpful for the advancement of science, particularly in the field of digital public relations, which helps researchers determine how much of an impact brand loyalty has on consumer loyalty. Especially in brand image science, and may offer suggestions to MS Glow on how to accomplish objectives in order to improve MS Glow's reputation with the public in general. Based on this background, the author is motivated to further explore how brand image affects MS Glow's customer loyalty

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Public Relations

Public relations theory has numerous implications, including acting as a particular management that can support, develop, and maintain channels of communication between companies and the public, acceptance of understanding, and collaboration, which involves managing difficulties or issues, may support management in staying informed, and also sensitive to public opinion [1].

According to the definition, it is clear that public relations is crucial for a business, organization, or government agency since they enable the maintenance of positive relationships and effective communication with the public and other organizations. Additionally, the organization or corporation in question will benefit from this in a number of ways, including having a positive public perception of it and being trusted by the general public, as well as being able to accomplish all of its objectives

B. Brands

Brand theory is a sign, name, design, or symbol used to distinguish one product or service from another in order to represent the identity of a person, group of people, or industry [2]. An influential brand may be identified by its widespread public awareness, which is a strong brand association with a specific product, a favourable opinion of the market, and a high level of brand loyalty from consumers. Of course, having a brand helps in many ways since a product or service needs a brand to exist.

Due to a recent trend on social media, where some users post their experiences with MS Glow products and the outcomes are undesirable, MS Glow products tend to be seen negatively in this research. Owing to this, many individuals are hesitant or unsure about purchasing MS Glow products, making it crucial for marketers to establish a strong brand image in the eyes of consumers.

C. Brand Image

A perspective of a brand that will represent customer memories and their associations with the brand is called brand image theory. Brand image is something that customer perceive and think when they see or hear something related to the brand [3]. A brand image is a compilation of perceptions pertaining to one of the interrelated brands present in human mind [4].

According to Keller (2013:78), there are three factors that affect brand image, including the strength of brand associations, which is dependent on how information enters the customer's memory, and the ability of sensory data associated with the brand to manage the information received. Favorability of the brand association, the benefit of brand association is that it fosters consumer trust, which means that the advantages the brand offers may satisfy customers' goals and requirements, resulting in the development of a positive and favorable attitude toward the brand.

Uniqueness of brand associations, in this circumstance, a brand has to have something intriguing and unusual so that the product has its own particular qualities and can subsequently be challenging for rivals to replicate. According to researchers, indicators from Keller (2013:78) are consistent with this study, which focuses on understanding how customers regard the product from three indicators based on the brand image indicators listed above and the opinions of other experts

D. Customer Loyalty

The commitment of customers or consumers to suppliers, retailers, or brands that is founded on positive attributes and is expressed in recurrent and consistent purchases is referred to as customer loyalty [5]. The indicators of customer loyalty based on the opinion of Kotler & Keller (2006) include Referrals, which refer to the entire existence of the industry. Retention, namely resistance to negative influences related to the industry, and Repeat Purchase, namely consumer loyalty when buying products [6].

E. Uses And Gratification Theory

The Uses and Gratification theory, according to its creators Elihu Katz, Jay G. Blumer, and Michael Gurevitch, looks at the psychological and social roots of needs that give rise to expectations from the media or other sources, different patterns of media exposure, need fulfilment, and other, possibly unintended effects [7]. Because today's audience is made up of active people who have a propensity for media literacy, the Uses and Gratifications theory may be applied to contemporary research

3. METHODOLOGY

Because the goal of this research is to determine if and how much the independent variable (X) and the dependent variable impact one another, the method used in this study is quantitative and employs a causal associative style of research (Y). Because the original foundation for MS Glow sales is in the Bali and Surabaya districts, researchers will focus on the people therein. The founder of MS Glow, Maharani Kemala (2019), also claimed that the possibility of MS Glow in Bali was increasing rapidly.

Therefore, the researcher chose the area in Bali as the population of this study. The criteria in this study were women aged 17 years to 40+. Furthermore, those who have used MS Glow goods and reside in the Bali region. A non-probability sampling strategy is used in this study. In order to acquire data that satisfy the needs or criteria of this study, incidental sampling, a non-probability sampling approach, is utilized since the population sampled is too vast.

The researchers used the Slovin technique to determine the sample size based on an estimated 993,900 women in Bali who are aged 17 to 40+. Based on the Slovin formula, the researchers obtained calculation results of 99.98, which were rounded up to 100. As a result, the researchers used 100 respondents who had a 10% tolerance level. The questionnaire for this study, which use the Google Forms platform, will thereafter be delivered to respondents who utilize MS Glow products.

In this study, there are seven steps of data analysis:

1. The first of which is a validity test to determine whether the questionnaire is valid or not. By administering a pre-test to 30 participants in this study, the researcher first examined the validity of the instruments. All of the instruments were deemed valid since the computed r value was higher than the r table value, which is > 0.361 .
2. A questionnaire used to examine the reliability of a variable is a reliability test. Therefore, using SPSS, researchers tested for dependability. It is clear from this that the questionnaire instrument is reliable because the reliability value was more than 0.6.
3. This study uses descriptive analysis to determine how brand image affects consumer loyalty of MS Glow.
4. By figuring out the scale value of the data collected from the survey results, MSI is a method for converting data. Researchers may easily convert ordinal data into interval data by using Microsoft Excel's Methods of Successive Interval (MSI) feature.

5. The Kolmogorov-Smirnov test is used in this study's normality test, and the conclusions drawn from the findings of the test's normalcy may be observed from: The data is deemed to be regularly distributed if the significance value is greater than 0.05. The data are not regularly distributed if the significance value is less than 0.05.
6. Simple linear regression analysis is used to examine the relationship between two or more variables, particularly to examine the pattern of relationships for which the models are incomplete or to determine how changes in a number of independent variables affect the dependent variable in a complex phenomenon.
7. Using data collected from a sample, hypothesis testing is a technique for evaluating a claim or hypothesis about a parameter in a population [8]. The T Test will be used by the author, according to Ghozali (2011, 98), a statistical test called the T Test is used to determine how much each independent variable contributes to the explanation of the contents of the dependent variable.

4. RESULT

A. Respondent Profile

100 consumers of MS Glow products who agreed to fill out questionnaires were surveyed by the author. According to the respondent profile, 100 respondents were researched, 69% of them work in the private sector and between the ages of 20 and 24, and the other 29% are based in Bali. In addition, it was discovered that 45% of the respondents had monthly skincare costs between \$200,000 and \$500,000

B. Results of Descriptive Statistical Analysis

According to the average percentage value, the findings of the descriptive statistical analysis in this study will explain each dimension and the respondents' responses to the respondents' questions.

Table 1: Brand Image Dimension

No	Questionnaire Statement	Total Score
Strength Of Brand Association (X1)		
1	MS Glow is a skincare brand that is known to many people.	90,25%
2	In the field of skincare MS Glow includes brands that are less remembered.	81%
3	The price of MS Glow products from the past to the present is always on the quality.	81,5%
4	The price of MS Glow products is now relatively high and does not match the quality	73,25%
Average Percentage		81,5%
Favorability Of Brand Association (X2)		
5	MS Glow offers safe products for all skin types	78,5%
6	MS Glow products provide side effects that are not good for the face	77,25%
7	My skin is suitable for using MS Glow products	73,5%
8	The quality of MS Glow products is still lacking compared to the quality of other skincare brands.	71,75%
Average Percentage		75,25%
Uniqueness Of Brand Association (X3)		
9	MS Glow is quite attractive compared to other local skincare brands	75,5%
10	MS Glow products look better than other skincare products	75%
11	MS Glow products are very varied compared to other skincare brands	75,5%
12	I'm tired of MS Glow products.	77%
Average Percentage		75,75%

Table 1: Customer Loyalty Dimension

No	Questionnaire Statement	Total Score
Repeat Purchase (Y)		
13	I will continue to use MS Glow	70,75%
14	I am interested in other MS Glow products that I have never purchased	76,25%
Average Percentage		73,5%
Retention (Y)		
15	I already believe in MS Glow and am not interested in buying another skincare brand	70,5%
16	I thought to find another replacement product MS Glow	69,5%
Average Percentage		70%
Referrals (Y)		
17	I would recommend MS Glow to others	77,5%
18	It's enough for me to use MS Glow products, other people don't need to know	81,5%
Average Percentage		79,5%

C. Methods of Successive Interval

The author initially converted the ordinal scale to an interval scale before doing simple linear regression analysis on the data. For this study, author employed Microsoft Excel's Methods of Successive Interval (MSI) to make it easier to convert ordinal data into interval data.

D. Normality Test

The Kolmogorov-Smirnov test was utilized in this study's normality test, which additionally benefited from the usage of SPSS software. As can be observed from the significant value, $0.200 > 0.05$, the findings are regularly distributed residual values

E. Simple Linear Regression

To ascertain if the variable (x) and the variable (y) have any impact on one another, this study employs basic linear regression (y).

$$Y = 0.240 + 0.473x$$

Based on the simple linear regression equation created using the aforementioned data, it can be deduced that the constant value is 0.240, indicating that the customer loyalty variable's value is 0.240. While 0.473 is the regression coefficient value. When the regression coefficient is positive, the findings demonstrate a positive effect on the brand image variable.

F. Hypothesis test

In this study the authors tested the hypothesis by using the T Test. The results of the T Test are as follows

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.640	1.551		1.057	.293
	Strength of brand association	1.242	.117	.732	10.631	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Loyalitas Pelanggan

Based on the results of hypothesis testing there is an influence between the strength of brand association and customer loyalty. The results obtained a t value of $10,631 > 1.98$. Therefore, it can be concluded that H_0 is accepted, which means that there is an influence between the strength of brand association (X1) on customer loyalty (Y).

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	3.872	.980		3.951	.000
	Favorability of brand association	1.160	.079	.829	14.688	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Loyalitas Pelanggan

Based on the results of hypothesis testing with T Test, it can be seen that there is an influence between favorability of brand association and customer loyalty. The results obtained a t value

of $14,688 > 1.98$. Hence, it can be concluded that H_0 is accepted, which means that there is an influence between favorability of brand association (X2) on customer loyalty (Y).

Model	Coefficients ^a					
	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		Sig.	
	B	Std. Error	Beta	t		
1	(Constant)	2.638	1.096		2.407	.018
	Uniqueness of brand associations	1.254	.088	.821	14.224	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Loyalitas Pelanggan

Based on the results of hypothesis testing with T Test, it can be seen that there is an influence between the uniqueness of brand association and customer loyalty. The results obtained a t value of $14,224 > 1.98$. On that account, it can be concluded that H_0 is accepted, which means that there is an influence between the uniqueness of brand association (X3) on customer loyalty (Y)

5. CONCLUSION

Based on the test results on the normality test, the residual value is normally distributed, which is seen from the significant value, namely $0.200 > 0.05$. The outcomes of basic regression analysis then demonstrate a positive effect on the brand image variables. Considering the descriptive analysis's findings, which indicate that the dimension of the strength of brand association falls into the very high category with an average percentage of 81.5%.

In the meantime, the brand association metrics of favorability and distinctiveness fall under the high category. The average percentage achieved is 75.75% for the dimension of brand association's uniqueness, and the lowest percentage is 75.25% for the dimension of brand association's favorability. Recurring purchases, retention, and referrals are all included in the high group, according to the findings of the descriptive study on the customer loyalty variable.

On the referrals dimension, which has the greatest value of the other 2 dimensions on the customer loyalty variable, the average percentage attained was 79.5%. While the average percentage value for the repeat purchase dimension is 73.5%, the lowest value for the customer loyalty variable component is 70% for retention. Based on the results of the hypothesis test using the T Test, it can be deduced that brand image can have an impact on customer loyalty for MS Glow because of the relationship between the strength of brand association, favorability of brand association, and uniqueness of brand association.

Customer loyalty and the impact of brand image MS Glow, in which case MS Glow's product quality must be improved. MS Glow, being a well-known skincare company, has to develop solid relationships with its clients in order to strengthen the loyalty of MS Glow customers. The degree of brand association has a large influence on customer loyalty; hence MS Glow must give clear and accurate information about its goods. As a result, a stronger relationship with MS Glow will be formed in the thoughts of customers in the future.

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